

CA20104 – Network on evidence-based physical activity in old age (PhysAgeNet)

Deliverable D4.4

*D4.4 Report on PhysAgeNet research and impact, including implementation of
measures to maximize impact*

CBO3

Contributors

Working Group 4

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1. INTRODUCTION

PhysAgeNet (COST Action CA20104) is a European network focused on promoting evidence-based physical activity in older adults. The network integrates interdisciplinary research and practice across Europe, aiming to enhance health outcomes and reduce inactivity-related burdens through innovative ICT solutions and open data frameworks.

The specific objective of this report addresses PhysAgeNet Capacity Building Objective 3 (CBO 3), which focuses on identifying and addressing research questions to foster new research proposals. **The report's purpose is to evaluate the PhysAgeNet impacts achieved, and the measures used to maximize them.**

2. RESULTS

2.1. An evaluation of impacts achieved

Defined in MoU	Communication channels, actions performed, relevant project outputs
Accelerate sharing of knowledge and experiences on current gaps and needs	<i>Activities within network – Conferences (2), Short-Term Scientific Missions/ STSMs (21), ITC grants (17), Virtual Mobility Grants/ VM (90), YRI = 4 (type of grant was added by COST-GP4), VNS = 4, collaboration with other COST Actions (DE-PASS, PROGRAMMING)</i>
Raise attention to knowledge gaps	<i>Activities within network- conferences (2), STSMs (3), ITC grants (9), VM (36)</i>
Spreading of knowledge about healthy ageing research concepts and research methods	<p><i>Training schools (3):</i></p> <p><i>GP2: From narrative to systematic living review (Kaunas, Lithuania)</i></p> <p><i>GP3: Artificial Intelligence meets Physical Activity (Ankara, Turkey)</i></p> <p><i>GP4: Evidence-Based Physical Activity in Older Age: Strengthening and Disseminating Research Design Standard (Gdansk, Poland)</i></p> <p><i>3 Webinars (planned October 2025)</i></p> <p><i>Collaboration with other COST Actions (DE-PASS, PROGRAMMING)</i></p> <p><i>Publications (17 peer-reviewed)</i></p>
Enhanced cooperation between basic research and applied research	<i>Proposals and Projects resulting from Action networking: 13+</i>

Building a data registry , fostering big data approaches, and integrating AI-based analysis tools	<p><i>D1.1. Database with references and metadata related to PA interventions and based on EBM</i></p> <p><i>D2.1. Compendium of legal, ethical and resource aspects for open data repositories.</i></p> <p><i>D2.2. Scientific literature status, requirements, and roadmap for the development of standards and utilisation of biomarkers, behavioural markers and environmental factors with open data.</i></p> <p><i>D2.3. Open data framework including PA intervention and multiple data sources and biomarkers</i></p> <p><i>D2.4. Demonstrator (prototype) of the repository including real data from technology-assisted PA interventions.</i></p>
Developing platforms for implementation of individual training	<i>FIT4Alz Fitness for Alzheimer, ERASMUS+ SPORT funded project, proposer Ana Filipa Silva (Portugal)</i>
Accelerate application of AI capabilities in PA training programs for older adults as a means to improve intervention outcomes within populations with diverse needs towards the development of tailored PA training	<i>Training School (GP3): Artificial Intelligence meets Physical Activity (Ankara, Turkey)</i>
Promoting public health	<p>Contribution of network members to public health policy and activities- network members as experts have served to various activities on national and international level.</p> <p>Relations with stakeholders described in D4.2.</p>
Facilitating the collaboration between members of the network	<p>Sharing the information about the project calls and interests for cooperation on network internal communication channels.</p> <p>Proposals and Projects resulting from Action networking (13+), Publications (17), Conferences (2), STSMs (21), ITC grants (17), VM (90).</p>

2.2. An evaluation of measures used to maximize the impact

Defined in MoU	Communication channels, actions performed, relevant project outputs
Knowledge creation	<i>D2.2. Scientific literature status, requirements, and roadmap for the development of standards and utilisation of biomarkers, behavioural markers and environmental factors with open data.</i>

<p>Transfer of knowledge & career development</p>	<p>WGs meetings STSMs (21) Virtual mobility (90) Training schools (3) Conferences (PhysAgeNet & EGRAPA) (2) ITC grants (17) Webinars (October 2025)</p>
<p>Knowledge dissemination and exploitation</p>	<p><i>SciCom plan</i> <i>D4.1. Design and set up of standard tools for internal and external communication, including logo, website and social media accounts.</i> <i>D4.2. Stakeholder Analysis Matrix, containing a list of stakeholders, their interests and influence on the topic.</i> <i>Horizon Results Booster (HRB) Module A- Portfolio of Research and Innovation Results Project Group: PhysAgeNet – CA20104 , DE-PASS- CA19101 and PROGRAMMING- CA21122</i></p> <p>PhysAgeNet website: https://physagenet.eu/ Other communication channels: https://www.linkedin.com/company/physagenet-cost-action/posts/?feedView=all https://x.com/physagenet</p> <p>Publications (17), see Appendix 1 Local activities of network members: <i>presentations and workshops with different stakeholders, open sessions during PhysAgeNet MC and WG meetings.</i></p> <p>Local activities of network members: <i>presentations and workshops with different stakeholders, open sessions during PhysAgeNet MC and WG meetings.</i></p>

2.3. Proposals and Projects resulting from PhysAgeNet activities

This section represents identified research questions regarding the present needs and addressing them through special interest groups and resulting in the project applications involving network members.

Nr.	Title	Name and country of main proposer	Number of proposers	Action participants listed among the proposers (Name and Country)	Action participants from outside academia among the proposers* (select YES, NO)	Funder* (select Horizon, Other EU, Trans-National, National, Industry, Other)	Amount requested / granted in EURO	Call identifier	Year submitted)	Result* (Select: under evaluation, under negotiation, funded, not funded, other)
1	EnRICH-HABITS: EmpoweRing Citizens to adopt Healthy lifestyle Habits: A data-enabled community-based citizen Science approach	Erja Portegijs (Netherlands)	4	Erja Portegijs (NL) Paolo Caserotti (DK) Signe Tomsone (LV)	No	[ZonMw, Innovation Fund Denmark & Latvian Council of Science] umbrella of ERA4Health Partnership (GA N° 101095426 of Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme).	839.704 €	Era4Health Health Equity	2023	Funded
2	MOBilité des séniors: entraînement COgnitif et Musculaire, étude des médiateurs neuro-biologiques (MOBICOM)	Antoine Langegard (France)	2	Antoine Langegard (FR) Evrin Gökce (TR)	No	Other (Université de Caen Normandy)	80.000 € (18 month salary)	FINANCEMENT DE JEUNES CHERCHEURS – 2023	2023	Funded
3	FIT4Alz Fitness for Alzheimer	Ana Filipa Silva (Portugal)	5	Ana Filipa Silva (IT),	Yes	ERASMUS+ SPORT	40.0000 €	101090386 – Fit4Alz	2022	Funded
4	Investigation of Physiological Biomarkers in Assessment of the Effects of Computer-Based Exercise on Muscle	Veysel Alcan (Turkey)	2	Veysel Alcan (TR) Fatma Kübra Cekok (TR)	No	TNational: arsus University Scientific Research Projects	1.413 €	MF23.001	2023	Funded

	Performance in Older People					Funding					
5	Feasibility of Using Smartphone Applications for Promoting Active Aging	Tiia Kekäläinen (Finland)	2	Tiia Kekäläinen (FL) Michael Brach (DE)	No	WiRe Womenin Research Fellowship Programme , University of Münster	7.700 €	n.A	2023	Funded	
6	Evaluation of the Effects of Exergame Exercises on Improving Balance and Foot Muscles in the Elderly Using Surface EMG and Postural Sway Analysis	Veysel Alcan (TR)	4	Veysel Alcan (TR) Fatma Kübra Çekok (TR) Kutluk Bilge Arıkan (TR) Ayşenur Çekok (TR)	NO	TÜBİTAK (Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye) 2515 - COST Action Members R&D Support Program	53.333 €	124E885	2024	Funded	
7	Agewell Europe	Diane Cooper (Ireland)	5	Michael Brach (DE)	YES	EU Erasmus	- 400-000€	2023-1-IE01-KA220-ADU-000159356	2023	Funded	
8	AI-Driven EEG Analysis for Migraine Sufferers	Salvatore Tedesco (Ireland)	IE, TR			Other EU-funding	42000 €	INFRACHIP (European Research Infrastructure on Semiconductor Chips)	2023	Funded	
1	European Fitness Monitoring System for 65plus	Patrick Esser (United Kingdom)	6	Patrick Esser (United Kingdom) Stevo Popovic (Montenegro) Iuliia Pavlova (UA)	Yes (E-SENIORS: INITIATION DES SENIORS AUX NTIC ASSOCIATION)	EU Erasmus	- 400000 €	ERASMUS-SPORT-2023	2024	Not funded	
2	EUFITMOS 65plus		6	7	Patrick Esser (UK)	No	EU-Erasmus	450,000	ERASMUS-SPORT-2024	2024	Not funded

				Iuliia Pavlova (UA)						
3	EUFITMOS 65plus	Iuliia Pavlova (Ukraine)	6	Iuliia Pavlova (UA) Patrick Esser (UK) Stevo Popovic (Montenegro)	No	EU – Erasmus	400.000 €	ERASMUS-SPORT-2025	2025	Not funded
4	Database for Saudi Seniors	Shaea Alkahtani (Saudi Arabia)	2	Shaea Alkahtani (SA) Michael Brach (DE)	No	International Scientific Partnership Program	70.000	KSI-ISPP-277	2025	Not funded
5	Living Review TBA	Michal Brach (Germany) Patrick Esser (United Kingdom)		Michael Brach (DE) Patrick Esser (UK)		EU – COST - CIG	125000 €	n.A.	2024	Not funded

2.4. PhysAgeNet outcomes for scientific and societal impact in long-term

To support the long-term impact and sustainability of the PhysAgeNet network, Working Group 4 (WG4) developed a targeted survey aimed at gathering ideas, priorities, and strategic directions from its members. The survey was designed to capture diverse perspectives across disciplines, career stages, and countries, and was distributed via an online form of WG4 Sustainability Survey.

Most important outcomes from PhysAgeNet with potential for scientific and societal impact in long-term:

Guidelines for Research:

- Framework for research improvement
- Recruitment guidelines
- Reporting guidelines

Guidelines for Interventions:

- Guidelines and framework for designing technology-assisted PA interventions
- Intervention programs implementing evidence-based PA interventions in older adults
- Guidelines for conducting physical activity programs

Education and Public Awareness:

- Importance of technology-assisted physical activity (TA PA)
- Diversity of the older population in TA PA interventions

Platforms for collecting:

- Best methods and practices.
- Evidence from different cultures and countries
- Open data structure, including PA intervention and multiple data sources and biomarkers
- Exercise protocols for older people with chronic diseases
- Research outcomes dissemination

Sustainability of the Network:

- Collaborations and partnerships to drive research and innovation in ageing
- Expertise of network members
- Collaboration in PhD supervisions
- Joint publications

New project proposals:

- Information exchange and awareness of different funding options
- Development of innovative technologies to support PA in older age

ANNEX 1. CO-AUTHORED ACTION PUBLICATIONS – PEER REVIEW. (PUBLISHED)

N r.	Title	First Author, Year	DOI/ISSN	Link	Type	Journal	Subject	(2) COST Acknowledgment Included? (2) COST Funds Used for Publication?
1	Evidence-based yet still challenging! Research on physical activity in old age	Michael Brach (2023)	10.1186/s11556-023-00318-3	Link	Commentary	BMC Springer	Geriatrics and Gerontology	(2) Yes (2) No
2	Effect of physical activity interventions on quality of life in older adults: a protocol for systematic review and meta-analysis	Nicola Lamberti (2023)	10.1097/MD.0000000000031801	Link	Protocol	Medicine	General Medicine	(2) Yes (2) Yes
3	Myokines as mediators of exercise-induced cognitive changes in older adults: protocol for comprehensive living systematic review and meta-analysis	Wouter Vints (2023)	10.3389/fnagi.2023.1213057	Link	Protocol	Frontiers	Cognitive Neuroscience; Aging	(2) Yes (2) Yes
4	Effects of chronic physical exercise on executive functions and episodic memory in clinical and healthy older adult populations: a systematic review and meta-analysis protocol	Soledad Ballesteros (2024)	10.1186/s13643-024-02517-0	Link	Protocol	BMC Springer	Diseases of older adults	(2) Yes (2) Yes
5	Role of sex and training characteristics on exercise effects on cardiovascular aging: protocol for	Emmanuel Gomes Ciolac (2024)	10.1186/s13643-024-02644-8	Link	Protocol	BMC Springer	Exercise, Cardiovascular ageing	(2) Yes (2) Yes

	a systematic review with meta-analysis of randomized trials							
6	Chronic exercise effects on overall depression severity and distinct depressive symptoms in older adults: A protocol of a systematic and meta-analytic review	Melanie Mack (2024)	10.1371/journal.pone.0297348	Link	Protocol	Plos One	Exercise, Depression, Older Adults	(2) Yes (2) Yes
7	Defining and reporting exercise intensity in interventions for older adults: a modified Delphi process	Bettina Wollesen (2024)	10.1186/s11556-024-00337-8	Link	Delphi survey	BMC EurRevAgingPhysAct	Exercise intensity, Older adults, Expert rating, Delphi process	(2) Yes (2) No
8	Effects of digital physical activity interventions on muscle mechanical function in community-dwelling older adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Carlo della Valle (2025)	https://doi.org/10.1186/s11556-025-00380-z	Link	Systematic review and meta-analysis	EurRevAgingPhysAct	Digital physical activity interventions, older adults	(2) Yes (2) Yes
9	Technology-Assisted Physical Activity Interventions for Older People in Their Home-Based Environment: Scoping Review	Rosemary Dubbeldam (2025)	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/B2NGD	Link	Scoping review	JMIR Aging	Aging	(2) Yes (2) Yes
10	The effect of physical interventions in	Emelyn Mathot (2025)	10.1093/geroni/igaf072	Link	Umbrella review of systematic reviews	Innovation in Aging	Physical exercise interven	(2) Yes (2) No

	older adults on inflammatory markers (IL-6, IL-10, CRP, TNF- α): an umbrella review of systematic reviews and meta-analyses				and meta-analyses		tions, inflamm ageing, circulating cytokines	
1 1	The Role of Environmental Factors in Technology-Assisted Physical Activity Intervention Studies Among Older Adults: Scoping Review	Carl-Philipp Jansen (2025)	10.2196/59570	Link	Scoping review	JMIR mHealth and uHealth	Environmental factors, intervention, older adults, physical activity, technology	(2) Yes (2) Yes
1 2	Key considerations and recommendations for recruiting older adults in physical activity studies	Sunwoo Lee (2025)	10.1186/s12874-025-02659-2	Link	Methodology paper	BMC Medical Reseah	Older adults; expert consensus; Delphi method	(2) Yes (2) Yes
1 3	Scoping Review of Psychological and Motivational Drivers of Adherence to Technology-Supported Physical Activity in Older Adults.	David Beckwee (2025)	TBA	TBA	Scoping review	EurRevAgingPhysAct	TBA	(2) Yes (2) Yes
1 4	Investigating the mediating effect of myokines on exercise-induced cognitive changes in older adults: A living systematic review and meta-analysis	Wouter Vints (2025)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2025.106381	Link	Living Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis	Science Direct	TBA	(2) Yes (2) No

1 5	Sclerostin as a biomarker of physical exercise in osteoporosis: A narrative review	Anna Oniszcuk (2022)	https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2022.954895	Link	Narrative Review	Frontiers	TBA	(2) No (2) No
1 6	Comparisons between bioelectrical impedance variables, functional tests and blood markers based on BMI in older women and their association with phase angle	Rafael Oliveria (2022)	https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19116851	Link	Study	Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health	TBA	(2) No (2) No
1 7	Cognitive Training with older adults using smartphone and web-based applications: a scoping review	Ana F. Silva (2024)	https://doi.org/10.14283/jpad.2024.17	Link	Scoping Review	Elsevier		(2) No (2) No